

Engineered living materials for sustainable and resilient architecture

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Progresses in biomimetics allow for the fabrication of man-made materials and surfaces with properties similar to biological ones. These advancements enable the development of a new generation of building materials for architecture that have remarkable properties typically unachievable with a traditional approach.

[H1]-Traditional building materials versus biomimetic materials

Human-made materials, including concrete, metal, plastic, bricks and asphalt, now exceed the overall living biomass on Earth¹. By 2050, the global population will rise to 9.7 billion people who will need a place to live. To accommodate this number of people, new buildings will need to be built, presumably from concrete, which is the most widely used building material in the world with around 30 billion tons of concrete used annually worldwide². The Paris Agreement and recommendations by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change state that limiting human-induced global warming to a specific level would require limiting cumulative anthropogenic CO₂ emissions³. For example, current production of concrete is responsible for 8% of global CO₂ emissions, and will need to be lowered by at least 16% by 2030 to be in line with the Paris Agreement⁴.

The required growth in housing offerings is unsustainable, and this situation is exacerbated by the poor longevity of most building materials. Buildings need to be protected against environmental and biotic degradation. However, common surface treatments, products and techniques consist of mineral oil binders and many environmentally unwanted ingredients, mainly biocides.

Scientists have turned to nature to address these challenges, as nature is a great source of inspiration for new scientific and technological achievements. Buildings can be developed with materials, structures and systems that imitate and respect their natural surroundings. Biomimicry is the practice of applying solutions developed by nature and translating its principles to human engineering. It is an elegant shortcut toward the optimization of design in many technological advances.

Engineered Living Materials (ELM) aim to outperform current examples of smart, active or multifunctional materials, enabling countless industrial and societal applications. ELMs are defined as materials composed, either entirely or partially, of living cells. Various microorganisms or engineered biological building blocks (proteins, polysaccharides and nucleic acids) can be incorporated as living and bioactive components in the form of a matrix or be a part of the living scaffold⁵. ELMs are an emerging product, but their development is expected to push the boundaries and frontiers of synthetic biology, materials engineering, nanotechnology, biomaterials and artificial intelligence. ELMs possess a broad portfolio of functionalities relevant for architecture (**Fig. 1**) and enormous potential for the building sector since they can replicate the function and capabilities of living organisms.

[H1] Bioinspired solution

Living organisms have developed smart, optimized and elegant solutions to survive, thanks to continuous selection and mutation processes during 3.8 billion years of evolution. Biological materials are often organized hierarchically, from molecular to nano-micro to macroscale. Consequently, the properties may vary at different levels, but all of them contribute to their multifunctionality.

According to Lurie-Luke⁶, materials account for around 50% of published research in biomimicry. In research and development, an interdisciplinary approach is nowadays promoted, which facilitates communication and knowledge transfer between materials scientists, engineers, biologists, designers and architects. This interdisciplinary approach promotes out-of-the box thinking, stimulates the development of an integrated perspective on the complexity of the scientific challenges and provides the scientific knowledge necessary to deeply understand solutions before their implementation. The intersection of advanced materials characterization and digitalization, computational analysis of biological functions, and data science enables the application of bioinspiration to further engineering findings. The past knowledge, skills and experience of collaborative teams facilitate problem solving and accelerate discovery. Bioinspired innovations can be approached from different perspectives: things that are created in nature can inform the development of new materials; the natural organization can inform potential shapes for man-made materials; the way organisms perceive can inspire a new generation of sensors; the way animals and plants move in their environment can inform advances in mechanics and kinetics; the way living organisms interact can inspire new ways of communication, and the way living organisms perform can inspire man-made processes⁶. Real breakthroughs, however, are frequently achieved through interdisciplinary and holistic ways.

[H1] Living materials in the building sector

Despite the recent progress in conventional material design and manufacturing, human-made materials possess limitations compared to materials developed by nature, in the range of their properties and the degree to which they are environmentally friendly and energy-efficient. ELMs have unique properties, such as embedded autonomy and responsiveness. They might be implemented as basic building blocks (self-healing concrete, self-growing bricks), insulation (active membranes) active elements (actuators, energy generators) or protective surfaces (coatings, paints). For example, bio-concrete (where limestone-producing bacteria are activated when a crack occurs) living active bio-composites, and self-healing coatings provide proofs of concept demonstrating the capabilities of ELMs.

Calcium carbonate is an essential component in the construction industry. A phenomenon called microbially-induced calcium carbonate precipitation (MICP) has received considerable attention. It is a naturally occurring process induced by microorganisms' activities that involves the formation and precipitation of CaCO_3 as a result of changes in the soil environment (pH, temperature, concentration and ratio of carbonate and calcium ions). MICP has been proposed as a potential tool to address many engineering and environmental issues associated with construction materials, because it is eco-friendly and relatively inexpensive⁷.

As opposed to concrete, which is an inorganic material, ELMs can be entirely biobased. The concept of a bio-composite where a fungus (*Ganoderma* sp.) partially decomposes the feedstock material and creates a dense hyphal mycelium network that binds together feedstock particles and fibers was upgraded by the re-introduction of a bacteria (*Pantoea agglomerans*), bringing new functionalities to the created material, such as the situ production of new molecules and synthetic sensing–signalling capabilities⁸.

As an alternative to bulk protection and biobased building blocks, an innovative and multifunctional coating system that relies on a biologically inspired concept for protecting materials is under development. Biofilms, an assemblage of surface-associated microbial cells enclosed in an extracellular polymeric substance matrix, are recognized as one of the most stable biological systems on earth. Biofilms are multicellular communities of various microorganisms surrounded by a hydrated matrix of extracellular polymeric substances (EPS). The EPS matrix provides mechanical stability to the three-dimensional biofilm structure, regulates the ability of the biofilm to adhere to surfaces and determines the ability of the biofilm to adsorb gasses, solutes and foreign cells. However, the beneficial use of biofilms for protection is nearly unexplored because up-to-date research is focused on preventing its formation. A prototype microbial coating built by an ubiquitous, yeast-like, oligotroph fungus (*Aureobasidium pullulans*) was designed to effectively protect surfaces of various substrates (concrete, stone, bricks, wood, steel, plastic), assuring optimal service life performance and desired functionalities including self-healing and bioremediation.

This pioneering design approach aims to push the boundaries of traditional materials toward the manufacturing of materials capable of interacting, adapting and responding to environmental changes. The development of new building materials benefiting from the synergistic power of active bio-based ingredients, living cells and nature-inspired mechanisms is in line with the recently published Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability and the European Green Deal priorities. Advancements in ELMs will contribute to the EU's 2050 long-term strategy for a climate-neutral Europe, by replacing fossil-based materials with renewable bio-based materials and boosting innovation for safe and sustainable chemicals⁹. The enhancement in performance due to the self-repair functionality will improve the environmental impact and reduce the cost burden of premature failure in service and maintenance activity. Finally, the ability to actively respond to external stimuli (temperature, humidity, pH, chemicals, electrical signals, light and force) makes such materials resilient and adaptable to climatic changes.

[H1] Outlook and future challenges

ELMs, though still emerging in the building sector, are present already as bulk and surface solutions. The successful implementation of biological systems in material science requires an in-depth investigation of their physical and biological constraints, such as proliferation, growth, shape change, strength and death. Current challenges associated with ELMs are related to upscaling, assuring the long-term viability of living cells, developing new fabrication technologies (for example, additive manufacturing should be adjusted to handle living cells, like in bioprinting), improving standardization and safety measures, and reducing potential barriers related to public acceptance. Nevertheless, besides inspiring materials development and boosting green architecture, the field of biomimetics provides a broader environmental perspective on how nature can evolve and contribute to the development of a green economy. Biomimetics is poised to make an impact on the advancement of new technologies that will lead to substantial scientific, societal and economic benefits in the near future.

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Competing interests

The authors declare no competing interests.

Figure 1. ELMs possessing unique functionalities, compared to traditional building materials represent a fundamental change in the production and performance of materials. Among novel functionalities are bioremediation (the ability to break down, change, remove, immobilize, or detoxify various physical and chemical pollutants), self-healing (built-in ability to automatically repair damages to themselves), antioxidant (the capability to inhibit production of free radicals), self-replication (the capacity to build of an identical or similar copy of itself), resilience (quick ability to recover from damage), signalling (the ability to receive, process, and transmit signals with its environment and

within itself), sensing (the ability to perceive and react to various signals), remodelling (the capacity of changing or altering the structure, style, or form), self-regulation (the ability to monitor and manage certain properties without intervention from external bodies), evolvability (the capacity of adaptive evolution).